

CONTINUOUS MONITORING OF RESIN CONTENT IN COMPOSITE PREPREG NARROW TAPES

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SUMMARY: The resin content is the critical factor to ensure the quality of the finished composites product. In response to the need for NDT procedure which can provide immediate information concerning resin content, we have undertaken research to develop a β -ray system that is capable of determining the resin content in the narrow prepreg tape with a width of 3-5mm on-line during unidirectional narrow tape impregnation process by presenting the data in a convenient and useful form. Using a system based on the difference of intensity attenuation with the diversity of resin content in prepreg, we have measured the GF/Epoxy, CF/Epoxy prepreg tapes. A series of calibration curves has been generated to evaluate the resin content in the same prepreg respectively. A good agreement with resin content has been shown by the β -ray system and the conventional weight method. The maximum deviation of resin content is approximately three percent, which indicates β -ray monitoring system is fit to measure the resin content in prepreg tapes.

KEYWORD: resin content, on-line monitoring, prepreg, β -ray monitoring system, intensity attenuation, NDT, composites

INTRODUCTION

Composites have steadily grown due to high strength-to-weight ratio and the requirement for quality assurance is increasing. The uniform resin distribution in prepreg is indispensable in ensuring the quality of the finished composites. Currently there are three basic methods to measure the resin content: solvent wash, acid digestion, and burn off. Generally, the sample is weighed when the resin is removed by the chemical action, combustion, and burn off. Then, the remaining fibers are weighed. From these data, the weight percentage of resin is calculated. Since these methods exhibit some disadvantages such as the high cost of disposing chemical wastes, health and safety concerns associated with the chemicals used, a lack of uniformity from operator to operator, and excessive time required to perform these tests, it can be concluded that NDT method must be improved. NDT methods that can overcome the disadvantages of current destructive methods, including the X-radiography, Eddy-current testing, photometer method, X-ray diffractometer technique[1,2], ultrasonic technique[3,4], and β -ray monitoring technology[5], etc., must be practiced. The β -ray measuring technology is the most effective means to determine the resin content on line.

Conventionally, the β -ray monitoring technology displays the amount of intensity transmitting from some features in the sample as a function of thickness over the sample. In practice, as far as the prepreg is concerned, the resin content is directly related to thickness if the fiber linear density is constant. Namely, it is expected the thickness of prepreg will increase as more resin is applied. Therefore, by using this approach, it is possible to determine the resin content in

prepreg narrow tape. The theory to establish the β -ray measuring system is that the intensity is attenuated when β -particles penetrate the prepreg. Consequently the attenuation corresponds to the exponential principle:

$$I = I_0 e^{-\mu\rho x} \quad (1)$$

where, I_0 and I are the intensities of before and after β -particles penetrating the sample respectively; μ is the material's absorption coefficient; ρ is the density of the measured material; x is the thickness of the measured material.

The method applied to the β -ray measuring system records the variation in intensity (I/I_0) due to β -particles penetrating prepreg tape. These parameters are then correlated to the resin content determined by the weight method in order to establish calibration curves for a set of different prepreg tapes. The calibration curves are subsequently used to safely evaluate the resin content in unknown samples of the same type.

EXPERIMENT

Experiment Instrument

The experimental instrument include a standard β -ray generator and a scintillation detector (which consists of a scintillate, a photo multiplier tube and an amplifier) and a computer, shown in Fig. 1.

Measurement of Dry Fiber

The first step in the experimental phase is to ascertain the extent of fluctuation of the linear density in dry fibers. The long fibers are continuously passed through the space between the β -ray generator and the detector. The β -ray intensity after transmitting the sample is recorded. Then, compared with the initial intensity I_0 , the attenuation quantity is calculated.

On-line Measurement of Resin Content

To measure the variation of the resin content in prepreg tapes on line, it is essential to install the β -ray measuring system in front of the take-up block during unidirectional narrow tape impregnation process. A pair of pressure rolls whose middle position dived a gap with a width of 4 mm is placed in front and in back of this system to ensure prepreg width being precisely 4mm. The effect of width on the accuracy of measurement is the most critical factor. A series of prepreg tapes of different resin content for the GF/Epoxy, CF/Epoxy have been measured using this system on-line. At the same time two calibration curves are established on the basis of the measured parameters.

Fig. 1: the schematic diagram of β -ray monitoring system

Weight Method Measurement on Resin Content

The conventional weight method, a type of destructive measurement, is utilized to determine the resin content in above prepreg tapes. The prepreg tape with a length of 20mm accurately cut from the continuous tape is weighed and the resin content is calculated, provided that the fiber linear density is constant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

To measure the resin content, the linear density of fiber is first analyzed. The results are listed in Table 1 and 2. From the data in Table 1, we find that the standard deviation is approximately 0.14 percent and the confidence relative deviation is only 0.2 percent, on the condition that the confidence degree is 90 percent and sample size is ten. This indicates that the distribution of GF is uniform, and ensures that the variation of intensity attenuation in the β -ray measuring system manifests the fluctuation of resin content in GF/Epoxy prepreg tapes. The same results are obtained in Table 2 about the CF. Moreover, we note that the extent of variation with the intensity attenuation due to the fiber passing through the measuring system varied significantly for different material systems. Since the densities of fiber vary, there should be a difference in the relationship between the intensity attenuation and the thickness for different fiber system, i.e., the fiber's density. So it is imperative to establish different calibration curves for each sample system. The experiment is based on the fact that the fiber linear density is constant. In cases where the fiber linear density dose vary, a solution would be to install another β -ray measuring system to determine the intensity attenuation aroused by the fiber before the fiber impregnating resin.

Table 1: the statistical analysis of GF density

I [KHz]	I/I ₀	W _f [g/m]	mean of W _f [g/m]	Standard deviation	Confidence interval	Confidence relative standard deviation
61.9	0.993	0.518	0.5184	1.35E-3	[0.5177,0.5191]	0.2%
61.0	0.980	0.520				
61.4	0.986	0.549				
61.6	0.989	0.517				
62.2	0.997	0.517				
62.1	0.996	0.517				
62.1	0.996	0.520				
61.8	0.992	0.520				
61.9	0.993	0.520				
62.0	0.994	0.517				

Table 2: the statistical analysis of CF density

I [KHz]	I/I ₀	W _f [g/m]	mean of W _f [g/m]	Standard deviation	confidence interval	Confidence relative standard deviation
71.8	0.792	0.953	0.9524	1.51E-3	[0.9515,0.9533]	0.19%
71.9	0.793	0.955				
71.6	0.789	0.951				
71.8	0.792	0.952				
72.0	0.794	0.953				
72.1	0.796	0.952				
71.7	0.790	0.951				
71.9	0.793	0.954				
72.0	0.794	0.950				
72.3	0.798	0.953				

where the confidence interval is calculated on the condition that the confidence degree is 90 percent and sample size is ten.

Fig 2: The calibration curve for GF

Fig.3: The calibration curve for CF

There are potential problems with using this system for resin content measurement related to the dependence of the thickness on fiber linear density. Keeping fiber linear density constant over the entire range of resin content has been done to ensure that changes in thickness could be correlated with variation in resin content. Based on this, a series of calibration curves, intensity attenuation (I/I_0) versus resin content determined with the weight method have been established for prepreg tapes with the different reinforcement, as shown in Fig.2 and 3.

By observing both calibration curves, the correlation coefficient in both figures is beyond 0.99, which is used reliable in evaluating the resin content in prepreg with the same type.

The Table 3 and 4 list the values of resin content determined by both the conventional weight method and the calibration curves. The maximum deviation is 2.8% for GF/Epoxy and 3.3% for CF/Epoxy by comparing the value in resin content determined with two measurement methods. It shows the β -ray monitoring system may, in comparison, accurately determine the resin content in prepreg tape and its results are more reliable. However, it must be noted that the sample's flutter, when going through the monitoring system, greatly affected the measurement precision since the sample's width contrasted to the β -ray generator may possibly change, and a part of β -particles directly come into the detector. So it is essential to minimize the flutter in the sample in order to precisely measure resin content.

Table 3: the analysis of resin content in GF/Epoxy prepreg tape

W_p	R%	I/I_0	R'%	relative deviation
0.292	28.9	0.75	29	0.3%
0.298	30.3	0.744	30	0.1%
0.305	31.9	0.720	33.0	3.4%
0.309	32.6	0.715	33.4	2.5%
0.322	35.5	0.682	35.0	1.4%
0.323	35.7	0.678	35.7	2.0%

Table 4: the analysis of resin content in CF/Epoxy prepreg tape

W_p	R%	I/I_0	R'%	relative deviation
0.272	29.9	0.695	29.0	3.0%
0.274	30.4	0.692	29.9	1.6%
0.277	31.2	0.690	30.9	1.0%
0.281	32.2	0.673	33.1	2.8%
0.284	32.9	0.659	34.0	3.3%
0.286	33.4	0.655	34.2	2.1%

where R% is the resin content determined by the weight method; R'% is that determined by comparing the calibration curve.

As far as the prepreg tape system is concerned, it consists of fiber and resin that adequately absorb β -particles, i.e., the intensity attenuation detected in the prepreg tape arises from two compounds acting together. Exponential parts of the equation may be displaced by:

$$\mu \rho \chi = \mu_m \rho_m \chi_m + \mu_f \rho_f \chi_f \quad (2)$$

The subscripts, m and f, separately stand for the resin and fiber. The equation may be shown as :

$$I/I_0 = e^{-\mu_m \rho_m \chi_m - \mu_f \rho_f \chi_f} \quad (3)$$

If the fiber linear density is constant, the intensity attenuation due to the fiber action may be constant K, then the equation is written as :

$$I/I_0 = Ke^{-\mu_m \rho_m \chi_m} \quad (4)$$

Taking advantage of the least square method, the absorption coefficient of resin is computed as 0.014 for the GF/Epoxy and 0.012 for CF/Epoxy.

Since within the system itself there exists a certain deviation such as the variation in the output intensity including the initial intensity (I_0) and the attenuated intensity (I), we will analyze the effects of these factors on the resin content.

First, presuming the initial intensity (I_0) is steady, we will consider that the variation in I contributes to the deviation of the resin content ($\rho_m \chi_m$). The change of I is written as:

$$dI/I_0 = Ke^{-\mu_m \rho_m \chi_m} (-\mu_m) d(\rho_m \chi_m) \quad (5)$$

i.e.,

$$dI / I = (-\mu_m) d(\rho_m \chi_m) \quad (6)$$

When the variation in I is 1 percent, the deviation of resin content will reach the 3.3 percent for the general purpose since the absorption coefficient (μ_m) range is at 0.01, which is not fit to determine the resin content. Due to the general demands, the relative deviation in resin content is about 1.0 percent and the weight percentage of resin content in prepreg tapes is 30, the relative variation to be under 0.3 percent is needed. The same results may be acquired presuming the I is consistent but the initial intensity (I_0) changes.

In other words, we will discuss the effect on the value of resin content when the absorption coefficient (μ_m) deviates if the β -ray measuring system is steady. According to the equation (4), we can write the relationship between the change in μ_m and the deviation in resin content as:

$$\frac{d(\rho_m \chi_m)}{d\mu_m} = - \frac{K'}{\mu_m^2} \quad (7)$$

Where $K' = \ln(KI_0/I)$. In the light of the equation (7) and the μ_m range at 0.01, that the slight change of absorption coefficient (μ_m) will product the serious error for evaluating the resin content may be turned out. So the measured prepreg tapes must be wholly consistent with

those used for calibration curve since μ_m is the most important factor to affect the measurement result.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, β -ray measuring system measures the parameters that are correlated highly with resin content, with the thickness being primary parameter. The slight deviation due to the combination with the weight method and the exponential deviation is acceptable. Moreover, by comparison with other measurement methods for resin content, it isn't essential to cut the sample from the roll, but directly measure resin content on line, which is very important to the manufacture of the prepreg tape.

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